

Livelihood improvement of farmers through fish farming in haor areas of Bangladesh

MA Hossain^{1*}, M Rashiduzzaman², MS Islam², KC Bhowmick³

¹Department of Animal Science, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

²Palli Daridra Bimochon Foundation (PDBF), Dhaka, Bangladesh

³Social Development Foundation (SDF), Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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*Corresponding Author

MA Hossain

✉ anwar.kbd82@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to determine the livelihood improvement of fish farmers through fish farming in Kulaura upazila under Moulavibazar district. The present livelihood situation of fish farmers was measured on the basis of five parameters namely the change in food intake, household condition, physical assets, sanitation and income by involvement in fish farming activities. Data were collected by using a pre-tested interview schedule through personal interviewing method during July 2017 to September 2017 from seventy five (75) fish farmers. The paired t-test was used to measure the comparative change 'before' and 'after' involvement in fish farming. The results revealed that food intake, housing condition, physical assets, sanitation and income were increased significantly among the respondents. Average food consumption was increased to 2268.20 Kcal from 965.15 Kcal, average housing condition increased to 2.89 from 1.49 which indicates move towards having building house, average physical assets increased to 40.77 from 15.85, sanitation increased to 2.75 from 1.32 which indicates move towards pucca latrine and income increased to 568 thousand to 473 thousand per year. The results indicate the improvement of livelihood of fish farmers by involvement in fish farming activities. The fish farmers were faced some problems like fish disease, over flood, lack of market facilities, high cost of fertilizer and fish feed, lack of knowledge in application of fish feed and fertilizer, unavailability of quality seed and species etc. Support from Department of Fisheries (DoF) and Non Government Organizations (NGOs) working in fisheries sector should be involved to mitigate these problems. In conclusion, livelihood would be drastically improved by fish farming of the farmers in the studied areas.

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is recognized as one of the most favorable country in the world for freshwater rural fisheries because of its resources and agro-climatic condition (Ahmed and Hasan 2007; Sheheli et al., 2014). Fish is the second most valuable agricultural crop in Bangladesh, play a crucial role in the livelihoods and employment of millions of people. The culture and consumption of fish therefore has important implications for national income and food security. Bangladeshi people are popularly referred to as "Mache Bhate Bangali" or "Fish and Rice makes a Bengali" (DoF, 2019). Fisheries in Bangladesh have both prospects and challenges. Fisheries sector is the one of the most productive and dynamic sectors which playing an

increasingly significant role in the economy for the last few decades. This sector is contributing a vital role in the socio-economic development and deserves potential for future development in the agrarian economy of Bangladesh. It contributes 3.50% to our national GDP and more than one-fourth (25.72%) to the agricultural GDP (DoF, 2019). This sector provides major share (60%) of all consumed animal protein. Bangladesh is blessed with vast and rich fisheries resources (DoF, 2019). The total output of this sector is 4.38 million tons of which 56.76 per cent were obtained from inland aquaculture, 28.19 per cent from inland capture fisheries and 15.05 per cent from marine fisheries (DoF, 2019). More than 12% of the total population of Bangladesh is engaged with this sector in full time and part time basis for their

livelihoods. It also has high potential for the perspective of economic development of the country. Bangladesh earns a considerable amount of foreign currencies by exporting fish, shrimps and other fisheries products (DoF, 2019). Around 400,000 ha of fish ponds/ditches and more than 900,000 households are involved in aquaculture (ADB, 2010; Sheheli et al., 2014). Creation of direct self-employment opportunities, fisheries expansion include the provision of nutrients, income generation for the poor, diversification of production and generation of foreign exchange earnings through export of high valued products (Hossain, 2009; Sheheli et al., 2014). About 12 million people (10 per cent of total population) directly or indirectly depend on fisheries sector for their livelihood. There are over 1.2 million fishermen in the country but almost two-thirds of them get involved in fishing during the monsoon. Fisheries play a vital role in rural poor people income generation as well as nutrient supply of 70 per cent people of Bangladesh live in villages (BBS, 2012; Sheheli et al., 2014). It is recognized that pond fisheries and fisheries of haors play a vital role in the livelihood earning of haor people. Large areas of Sylhet, Mymensingh, Sunamganj, Habiganj, Moulvibazar, Kishoreganj and Netrokona districts are covered by many haors. The haor basin has its commercial and ecological importance for fish production (Salauddin and Islam, 2011; Sheheli et al., 2014). Haors and beels support major subsistence and commercial fisheries. Although the rapid growth of haor fish production has resulted in large increases in the aggregate volumes of fish production, much of their areal expansion has taken place through the enclosure and conversion of seasonal floodplains. These changes have indicated in reductions of wild fish biodiversity and biomass, as well as exclusion of poor fisheries from access to them (Sultana, 2012; Sheheli et al., 2014). Moreover, haor areas are very much vulnerable area with diversified problems shortage of food, and damage due to floods, erosion, excess rain and cyclones, loss of land, earth quake (DoF 2009). In addition, the fish production of haor is decreasing day by day of rampant harvesting of other fish, lack of river velocity for brood, huge use of agrochemicals, high population pressure, natural sedimentation on haor basin, destruction of habitats (Ahmed, 2012; Sheheli et al., 2014). In haor areas people have

fewer opportunities by overcoming income generating activities that's why their livelihood largely depends on fisheries sector. Hence, fisheries sector is very much crucial despite of the declination of fish production in haor areas. The present study was carried out to evaluate the role of fish farming for improving the livelihood of fish farmers in haor areas of Bangladesh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted at three villages namely Bhukshimoil, Dakhina bazar and Magura of Kulaura Upazila under Moulvibazar district. These villages were purposively selected because fish farming of these areas was higher than other areas of Kulaura Upazila. Farmers were randomly chosen from each village. People of these areas are highly dependent on haor fish farming practices for their livelihood (DoF, 2019). These areas were selection based on the suggestions made by Upazila Fisheries Officer (UFO) and other relevant officials such as Upazila Rural Development Officer, Upazila Agriculture officer etc. of Kulaura Upazila of Moulvibazar.

Selection of beneficiaries

The research team pays more attention in selecting the beneficiary. Targeting right household is crucial not only for successful intervention of the project but also its sustainability issue. Hence, the research team sat together and consults with other relevant experts in developing the selection criteria. More importantly, comments and suggestions were made during inception meeting incorporated in developing the selection criteria. The total numbers of fish farmers in these three villages were 350 which constituted the sampling population. In the second step 34 per cent of the fish farmers were selected as sample by random sampling. Seventy five (75) fish farmers were selected and constituted the sample for this study. Both qualitative and quantitative data were used in the study. The research team interviewed the sample fishermen at their houses and/or farm sites. Data were collected through the pre-tested interview schedule by face-to-face interview procedure during the period of July 2017 to

September 2017. The interviews, lasting about three and half hours per day, focused on their existing and previous livelihood condition. The researchers were collected first hand idea and information about villages, local people, resources, institutions, infrastructure and public services through informal discussion with local people, local elite, and personnel of different organization working in the locality. Cross-check interviews were conducted with Local Extension Agent for fisheries officer, researchers and relevant non-government organization (NGO) workers.

Determination of livelihood improvement of fish farmers was the main objective of the study. The five selected criteria were used to determine the livelihood improvement. These were: change in food intake mainly protein, change in housing condition, change in physical assets, change in sanitation and change in increasing scope of income. The livelihood improvement was measured comparing to the average results of previous condition (recall data of five years) and present condition considering these five criteria. An index value was developed based on above elements for every household. Moreover, an aggregate value was estimated for selecting the beneficiaries. In the second step 34 per cent of the fish farmers were selected as sample by random sampling. Seventy five (75) fish farmers were selected and constituted the sample for this study. Both qualitative and quantitative data were used in the study. The problems faced by the farmers on fish farming which hindered their livelihood improvement was also determined. Using a four point rating scale such as high, medium, low and not at all. The possible range of problem score for each respondent could be '0' to '30' a total score of '0' indicated no problems in respect to utilize support services while a score of '30' indicated highest problem. Problem confrontation score was measured and a ranking order was done on the basis of this score. For each problem the score ranged from 0 to 180.

Sampling

Simple Random Sampling Technique has been used to select respondent households to perform baseline survey. All working villages have been used to select respondent households using the

Probability Proportionate Sampling to Size (PPS). Accordingly, 75 households have been selected using simple random technique from the sampling frame (population) of 350 households (HHs) from three working villages to conduct baseline survey for collecting specific information. Data were collected by trained enumerators. Collected data have been edited and entered into computer and analyzed using SPSS software by the consultant team. In the Baseline survey both qualitative and quantitative data were collected with direct interview method with the poor people through structured pretested questionnaire. People in the Moulovibazar district were not habituated in keeping written documents on various factors change in food intake mainly protein, change in housing condition, change in physical assets, change in sanitation and change in increasing scope of income. They replied to various questions by the trained field enumerators from their memories. Some response errors during interview were minimized by the researches.

Statistical analysis

Data were tabulated and analyzed with descriptive statistical method by fulfilling the objectives of the study. Tabular technique was applied for the analysis of data using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency, average and percentages through SPSS- v-16 version computer software. Paired t-test was done to measure the significant difference between 'before' and 'after' involvement in fish farming.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Change in food intake

The change in food intake is a good indicator for the improvement of livelihood. Increase in income raised the capacity of people to spend more money on diversified food. Average per capita per day calorie intake of the respondents before involvement in fish farming was 1181.28 kcal which was improved to 2312.50 kcal after the families were intensively involved in fish farming. According to the food consumption score, the respondents were classified into three categories following the household income and expenditures survey, FAO, (2000) such as "Below poverty line

(Hard core poverty) = up to 1805 k cal”, “Below poverty line (Absolute poverty) =1806-2122 k cal” and “Upper poverty line = >2122 k cal” (Sheheli et al. 2014). The average food intake of the respondents was in the upper poverty line after involvement in fish farming. As the result indicates more than 75% cent fish farmers upgraded from below poverty line to upper poverty line. As a result, their total calorie intake is significantly high as because of taken daily diversified food items in the studied areas.

Change in housing condition

As the livelihood condition improves, people had a tendency to reconstruct and improve their housing condition. The study reveals that 77.13 per cent of the respondents’ families had tin made house, 22.87 per cent of the respondents’ families had half building and no one had building before involvement in fish farming. After involvement in fish farming 55.88 percent of the respondents’ families had half building and 43.02 percent respondents’ families had full building. Fewer (1.1%) had tin made house in the studied areas. This results indicated that the intensive involvement in fish farming increased the ability of the fish farmers to spend extra money on their housing condition for their improving living condition. Improvement of housing condition was a major priority of villagers as their income generation increased. Due to the involvement in fish farming the fish farmers were able to keep some money even after the fulfillment of basic needs which they spend to improve their house in maintaining social status and participation of socio-cultural ceremony in different institutions and relatives residents for mental satisfaction.

Change in physical assets

As the income increases, the people try to keep hold of more physical assets for their future security. So, enrichment in physical assets was a vital indicator for determining the improvement of livelihood. The study showed that before involvement with fish farming 45.5% respondent families had low asset possession, 40.6% families had medium asset possession and only 2.1% family had high asset possession. After involvement in fish farming 70.2% respondent

family had medium asset possession and 65.5% families had high asset possession. Regarding average family asset score, the asset possession score of the respondent family increased to 40.77 from 15.85 due to their involvement with fish farming activities. This significant change in asset possession was definitely a positive change in their livelihood by alleviating their poverty. It also indicated strengthening their power to hold on assets and made a mark for their own in the society.

Change in sanitation

The condition of sanitation of a household indicated their livelihood condition. The development in sanitation facilities marks for the livelihood improvement status of the fish farmers in the studied areas. The study revealed that 40.0 per cent of the respondents’ families used bushes or open place, 35.0 per cent of the respondents’ families used *katcha* toilet and there was none to use sanitary toilet before involvement in fish farming. But after involvement in fish farming 12.5% of the respondents’ families used *katcha* toilet and 87.5% respondents’ families used sanitary toilet and not a single household members used buses or open place by buildup awareness in the studied areas. Gradually increasing the percentage of respondents using sanitary toilet was a sign of awareness building purely on the basis of health and sanitation among the beneficiaries. On the other hand it indicated the positive livelihoods improvement due to involvement in fish farming. As a result, fish farming increased the income of the fish farming household which support them to spend more money for improving the sanitation facilities including sanitary toilet and tube-well. After involvement in fish farming most of the households were used pure drinking and arsenic free water in the studied areas.

Change in increasing scope of income

Increasing facilities of income was a major indicator for livelihood improvement of the farmers. The scope of income increased, it showed the ability of people for improving their livelihood status. From the study, it was observed that the average income increased from 473 thousand to BDT 568 thousand per year. This result was not

similar to the findings of Mondal et al, (2012). Before involvement in fish farming 4.3% respondent had low income, 42.3% respondent had medium income and 53.4% respondent had high income. After involvement in fish farming 2.5% respondent had low income, 10.5% respondent had medium income and 87% respondents had high income. Every other facility comes with the increased income of the people. So, increased scope of income helps the respondents to spend more money of facilities that improves their livelihood status. It indicated that the income increases and livelihood improves was found due to involvement in fish farming.

Comparative change in terms of before and after involvement in fish farming

The significant change in relation to change in food availability, household, physical asset, sanitation and income of the respondents after their involvement with fish farming activities are shown in the Table 1. It indicated that the rate of calorie intake had increased after the involvement in fish farming. The food consumption habit of the fish farmers became better due to fish farming as they were more exposed to fish protein intake. The t value (20.484) also indicated of improvement in food consumption. It was seen that the housing

condition of the respondent of fish farmers had improved due to involvement in fish farming. This result was supported by the t value (22.034) as it indicated the significant improvement in housing condition due to fish farming. The results also indicated that the physical asset possession of the respondent fish farmers had increased after their involvement in fish farming. The t value (13.985) showed a positive change in physical asset possession between before and after involvement with fish farming. This also provided them more confident in the society. It revealed that the sanitation condition of the respondents had improved due to involvement in fish farming. This was on purely basis of indication of improvement for their sanitation, which was furnished by the t-value (22.151). Always using better sanitation ultimately improved the livelihood condition of the fish farmers in the studied areas. The family income of the fish farming respondent had increased due to involvement in fish farming IGAs. This was clearly indicated an improvement of the income, which was furnished by the t-value (13.998). As the income generation increased the fish farmers were used to habituate to expense more money for their improved livelihood status. The results did not agree with the findings of Sheheli et al. (2014).

Table 1: Comparative change of farmers in terms of before and after involvement in Fish farming

No	Dimensions of poverty	Mean		t value
		Before	After	
1	Food intake (k cal)	965.15	2268.20	20.484*
2	Household (score)	1.49	2.89	22.034*
3	Physical asset (score)	15.85	40.77	13.985*
4	Sanitation (score)	1.32	2.75	22.151*
5	Income (Thousand BDT Per year)	473	568	13.998*

Problems faced by fish farmers

The respondents of the studied were facing a number of problems while involving in fish farming activities. Ten problems in connection with fish farming were included in problems confrontation scale. The results showed that the highest proportion 71.5% of the respondents had high problems whereas 28.5% of them had medium problems of the fish farmers on fish

farming income generating activities (IGAs) (Table 2). There was none with minimum problems in the studied areas. It was considered that the fact of overall majority of the respondents faced from medium to high problems in fish farming IGAs, it could be concluded that updated digital measures should be undertaken to relief these barriers for encouraging the respondents of haor areas in fish farming IGAs. These results were in accordance with the findings of Sheheli et al. (2014).

Table 2: Distribution of fish farmers according to overall problems

Respondents category	Respondents No.	per cent	Mean	Standard deviation
Low problem (up to 10)	0	0		
Medium problem(11-30)	20	28.5	33.33	3.78
High problem (> 30)	55	71.5		

Ranking of the respondents by problem confrontation score

The respondents were ranked according to their problems faced to improve the livelihood condition was shown in the Table 3. It revealed that in the studied areas, most of the respondents had problem of 'fish diseases' as the major problem of fish farming in haor areas. Most of the respondents reported that the over flooded problem and it was ranked as the second problem. 'Lack of market facilities' was the third problem of the fish farmers. However, inadequate knowledge on site selection was the least problem faced by the respondents. As the haor areas are abundant with natural resources, so their controlling condition was beyond their capacity. As results there were occurred more uncontrolled fish diseases. They had no idea on these uncontrolled diseases. Haor are inundated areas of land. So, flooding is a common incident during the

monsoon seasons. The communication system was not so good in these areas which hamper the proper marketing of fish captured in the haor areas. As a result, they were deprived from real prices of fishes in the haor areas. Due to lack of different facilities, the haor farmers were deprived of some basic requirements such as education, health treatment, safe environment and recreation etc. Lack of education hinders them to understand the proper selection of fish species as well as benefits and limitations of using several fish feed and fertilizers. The price of feed and fertilizers was increasing day by day. The present study was almost agreed with the findings of Sheheli et al. (2014). So they needed better financial support to utilize their resources to the maximum production of fish. Proper credit and low interest rate could be mitigated this issue. So GO and NGOs play a vital role to overcome the financial support for fish farmers in the haor areas.

Table 3: The rank order of the respondents according to problem confrontation score

Problems	Level of problems				Mean	Problem confrontation score	Ranking order
	High	Medium	Low	Not at all			
Fish disease problem	45	25	5	0	3.38	203	1
Over flooded problem	44	22	9	0	3.46	188	2
Lack of marketing facilities	44	21	10	0	2.69	168	3
Lack of knowledge on application of fish feed and fertilizer	45	20	10	0	2.75	167	4
High cost of fertilizer and fish feed	37	28	10	0	2.78	162	5
Lack of financial support	40	26	9	0	2.59	155	6
Not availability of quality seed and species	55	20	10	0	2.44	148	7
Poor extension service	42	23	10	0	2.4	146	8
Lack of knowledge on species selection	41	24	10	0	2.487	144	9
Inadequate knowledge on site selection	36	29	10	0	2.75	118	10

CONCLUSIONS

Due to involvement in fish farming the extent of livelihood improvement of the farmers has been increased positively in respect of food intake, housing, physical assets, sanitation and income generation. As a result, fish farmers got the opportunity to spend the earned money in diversified sectors other than fulfilling just the basic requirements. On the other hand, some problems were observed among the respondents regarding fish cultivation which could be easily solved by awareness building of fish farmers with direct contact to upazila and district fisheries office and other fish culture community in the studied areas. Therefore, Government and other related organizations should be initiated some programs to improve the knowledge and skill of the fish farmers of haor areas about the selection of fish species, disease of fish, controlling measures, feed and fertilizer used. Proper training, refresher's training course, exposure visit etc. could be arranged to make fish farmers for achieved more skill and knowledge to solve the text mentioned problems.

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